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Thermally Coupled Modelling and Experimental Investigation of Electrooxidation for Reactive Black 5 Degradation

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Abstract

Objectives: To study the electrooxidation of Reactive Black 5 along with development of a thermally coupled model and to better predict degradation behaviour under varying operating conditions. **Methods:** The experiments were conducted using a mixed metal oxide anode for dye concentrations of 400–800 ppm at 22.5 V. A COMSOL Multiphysics® model. A pseudo first-order kinetics was developed in two versions—one with isothermal and another with thermal coupling. The model predictions were validated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and normalized Root Mean Square Error (nRMSE) values. **Findings:** It was observed that COD removal was higher at lower concentrations. The values reached around 70–75% at 400 ppm and decreased to around 45–50% at 800 ppm experimentally. The isothermal model captured these trends but overpredicted removal at higher concentrations, with values in the range 85–90%. The thermal effects were later introduced in the model. This resulted in improved adherence with experimental data. It reduced the RMSE from 0.21 to 0.1 and stabilized nRMSE within 12–20%, compared to earlier variations up to 50–55%. A temperature rise from 30°C to 90°C was observed. This was found to substantially influence reaction kinetics and overall degradation behaviour. **Novelty:** A thermally coupled multiphysics model incorporating temperature effects with improved prediction accuracy and a more realistic representation than conventional isothermal electrooxidation model was developed.

Keywords: Electrooxidation; Reactive Black 5; Multiphysics Modelling; Thermal Effects; COD Removal

1 Introduction

Discharge of dye-containing wastewater from textile and allied industries remains an obstinate environmental concern due to the presence of chemically stable and non-biodegradable compounds. These pollutants are resistant to conventional biological and physico-chemical treatment methods, thereby resulting in incomplete degradation and long-term environmental effect.

Electrochemical oxidation (EO) has emerged as a viable alternative, primarily due to its ability to generate strong oxidizing species in situ without the addition of external reagents. Recent studies have shown better degradation efficiencies using advanced electrode materials such as mixed metal oxides (MMO) and boron-doped diamond (BDD), along with optimized reactor configurations^{(1), (2), (3), (4)}. Also, advancements in methods like electro-Fenton and hybrid oxidation processes have further enhanced treatment performance for dyes such as Reactive Black 5^{(5), (6)} which has been taken as the dye under study for this present paper. However, it has been seen that the efficiency of the process depends on factors like operating conditions, electrode composition, and system configuration. Thereby making the process difficult to generalize or scale reliably.

Current studies focus majorly on experimental results that too under specific conditions. However, this makes it difficult to predict system behaviour across varying concentrations and operating regimes. Usually, the effect of combination of various modules like reaction kinetics, temperature variation, and system dynamics is often simplified or neglected. Thus, the resultant models either assume isothermal conditions or fixed kinetic parameters, which thereby leads to significant deviations of predictions from actual experimental results at higher pollutant loads^{(2), (5)}. Hence it can be safely concluded that the lack of integrated models that consider these interactions remains a key limitation in the current literature.

Recent publications have explored multiphysics modelling to address these challenges, with use of softwares such as COMSOL Multiphysics®. A combination of various physics like electrochemical reactions with transport processes have been investigated^{(7), (8)}. However, many of these models still do not explicitly incorporate thermal effects, even though temperature rise during electrooxidation is known to influence reaction kinetics and overall system behaviour. This gap becomes particularly relevant in high-concentration systems, where exothermic effects can alter degradation pathways and prediction accuracy. A comparative overview of recent modelling and electrochemical treatment studies is presented in Table 1.

In this context, the present study aims to address these limitations by combining experimental investigation with a thermally coupled multiphysics modelling approach for the electrooxidation of Reactive Black 5 using an MMO anode system. The work specifically focuses on integrating temperature-dependent kinetics within the modelling framework to better represent real system behaviour. By doing so, it seeks to improve predictive accuracy across a range of operating conditions and provide a more reliable basis for process understanding and optimization. The inclusion of thermal effects within a simplified yet representative model distinguishes this study from conventional isothermal approaches and contributes toward more realistic simulation of electrochemical wastewater treatment systems.

The key concepts of this study are summarized below:

- A thermally coupled electrooxidation model is developed by incorporating temperature-dependent kinetics. None has been developed so far.
- Model predictions are quantitatively validated using RMSE and nRMSE across a range of dye concentrations
- Improved predictive accuracy is demonstrated in comparison with conventional isothermal models
- A simplified yet effective modelling framework is proposed, balancing computational efficiency with realistic system representation

2 Methodology

2.1 Electrode Material Considerations for Model Validation

Selection of electrode is critical for accurate electrooxidation modelling and its practical application. Properties like activity, stability, and adaptability ensure wide use of mixed metal oxide (MMO) anodes based on Ti-supported RuO₂, IrO₂, and TiO₂-based ternary systems^{(2), (4), (17), (18)}. High catalytic activity and corrosion resistance provided by Ti/TiO₂-RuO₂ gives effective COD reduction. Ti/TiO₂-IrO₂ offers greater stability under oxidation conditions^{(18), (19)}. Ternary systems like Ti/TiO₂-RuO₂-IrO₂ combines the advantages of both the aforesaid systems and thereby achieves effective decolorization⁽²⁾. It has been seen that higher or comparable Ir content improves consistency, manipulating modelling parameters such as current distribution and mass transfer^{(4), (17)}. The COD removal ranges from 50% to 93% thereby supporting its selection for this study^{(4), (17)}.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of recent studies on RB5 electrooxidation and modelling approaches

Sr. No	Work presented	Software / numerical approach	Reported outcomes	Gap vs present work	Reference
11	Electrochemical degradation of 2-chlorophenol in a flow-by reactor operated in batch recirculation using axial dispersion+CST formulation	COMSOL Multiphysics (parametric model; axial dispersion + continuous stirred tank ODE)	Achieved excellent agreement between simulation and experiments ($R^2 \approx 0.98$, low RMSE); demonstrated effectiveness of lumped/parametric EO models for predicting pollutant decay	Does not study RB5; single reactor only; BDD electrode; no thermal coupling. Present work extends non-spatial modelling to single tank, includes exothermic effects, lab-synthesised Ti-TiO ₂ -RuO ₂ -IrO ₂ MMO	(9)
22	Pilot-scale electrochemical reactor for emerging pollutants with analysis of current distribution and reactor design	COMSOL Multiphysics (secondary current distribution + CFD coupling)	Numerical results guided reactor design; predicted trends matched pilot experimental performance	Focused on pilot reactor and BDD electrodes; spatially resolved fields emphasized	(10)
33	Hydrodynamic optimisation of an electrochemical flow reactor using numerical flow analysis	ANSYS Fluent (CFD)	Identified dead zones and improved flow uniformity; experimental validation confirmed CFD predictions	Only hydrodynamics simulated; no electrochemical kinetics, no COD prediction, Present work models reaction kinetics, energy consumption, and reactor configuration effects	(11)
44	Bubble-induced convection and mass-transfer enhancement in electrochemical systems	CFD / FEM multiphase numerical models	Demonstrated significant impact of gas evolution on local mass transfer and reaction enhancement	Focused on microscale bubble dynamics; not suited for reactor-level performance prediction	(12)
55	Fully 3D electrochemical reactor modelling of species transport and electric fields	COMSOL Multiphysics (3D FEM)	Accurately predicted concentration and potential fields at electrode scale; high computational cost	Highly detailed spatial model; no reactor-configuration comparison,	(13)
66	Electrochemical systems with coupled heat generation and temperature effects	COMSOL Multiphysics (Electrochemistry + Heat Transfer modules)	Demonstrated that non-isothermal modelling improves prediction of electrochemical performance	Generic electrochemical systems studied; no dye EO.	(14)
77	Review of EO reactor designs and modelling approaches	Review of CFD, FEM, and parametric models	Identified dominance of empirical and spatially intensive models; highlighted need for design-oriented modelling	Confirms research gap addressed by present work: lack of validated, non-spatial, energy-aware models comparing reactor configurations	(15)
88	Electrooxidation of Reactive Black 5 (experimental focus)	No numerical modelling	Reported high COD and colour removal efficiencies; provided benchmark experimental RB5 data	No modelling, no predictive framework. Present work bridges experiment and modelling	(16)

2.2 Experimental Setup

2.2.1. Chemicals, Reagents and Materials

A titanium substrate coated with a mixture of titanium dioxide, iridium dioxide, and ruthenium dioxide fabricated in the laboratory was used as the anode. The composition consisted of 50% TiO_2 , with the remaining portion equally divided between RuO_2 and IrO_2 . Standard thermal decomposition (STD) method was used for coating application. Stainless steel was used as the cathode. Synthetic wastewater was prepared using Reactive Black 5 dye dissolved in distilled water. The solution pH was maintained in the range of 2 to 2.2 using hydrochloric acid. Experiments were conducted at different initial dye concentrations. Concentrations in the range of 400 ppm to 800 ppm were used to study the effect of pollutant loading on system performance. The selected concentration range also allowed stable model development by avoiding excessive reaction saturation and ensuring consistent system behaviour during simulation.

2.2.2. System Description

The experiments were carried out in a 1 L magnetically stirred glass beaker. The MMO anode and stainless-steel cathode were placed at a specific inter electrode distance and connected to a DC power supply. A constant potential of 22.5 V was applied throughout the operation. Each experiment was conducted for a duration of 105 minutes. Samples were collected at regular intervals of 15 minutes from the start of the electrooxidation process till the end of the aforesaid duration. The experimental setup used for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Experimental Setup of a Single Tank batch reactor

2.2.3. Analytical Techniques

The treatment performance was evaluated primarily through Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) measurements using the open reflux method, in accordance with IS 3025 (Part 58): 2023. Colour removal was determined using a spectrophotometric method based on APHA Method 2120-C (24th Edition, 2023)⁽⁴⁾. Even though experimental results provide direct insight into system performance, a modelling approach is used in the following section to support interpretation and achieve a predictive setup which may extend the analysis beyond the current tested conditions.

2.3 Modelling and Simulation Approach

To further examine the behaviour of the system, a simulation-based approach was adopted. Two versions of the model were developed, one with isothermal conditions and the other integrating temperature effects observed during the process.

2.3.1. Software and Modelling Environment

COMSOL Multiphysics® was used in this study to simulate the electrooxidation process. It integrated reaction kinetics, mass transport behaviour, and thermal effects within a single model setup. The Electrochemistry Module was selected to represent the system in a simple lumped form, where changes in concentration and temperature were tracked as a function of time. The model was developed using kinetic parameters recorded from experiments. Appropriate boundary conditions were selected so that the simulated results could be directly compared with the observed COD reduction trends making it feasible while still describing the behaviour of the system under different operating conditions^{(7), (8), (9), (14), (20), (21), (22)}.

2.3.2. Assumptions

A set of basic assumptions were taken to ensure that the model remains computationally efficient along with incorporation of the essential behaviour of the electrooxidation system. These assumptions help in reducing unnecessary complexity and allow the focus to remain on the dominant reaction and thermal effects governing the system.

Common Assumptions:

- The electrooxidation reaction is assumed to be irreversible under the given operating conditions.
- The system is considered well mixed, ensuring uniform concentration (and temperature, where applicable) within the reactor.
- Dye degradation follows pseudo–first-order kinetics, which is commonly applied when oxidant availability remains relatively stable⁽¹¹⁾.
- The reactor operates at constant volume, with no change in system boundaries during the process.
- Mass transfer limitations are neglected, and the reaction is treated as kinetically controlled.
- Diffusion layer effects near the electrode are not explicitly considered, and the system is assumed to be bulk-controlled.
- The model is represented using a lumped parameter approach, with spatial variations neglected and system behaviour described as a function of time.

Model-Specific Assumptions:

(1) Initial (Isothermal) Model

- The system is treated as isothermal, and any temperature variation during the reaction is neglected.

(2) Thermally Coupled Model

- The exothermic nature of the electrooxidation process is considered, with heat generation linked to reaction progression.
- Temperature rise during the reaction is assumed to influence system behaviour, and thermal effects are incorporated through a simplified energy balance approach^{(14), (23)}.

2.3.3. Governing Equations

The electrooxidation process was modelled using a lumped formulation in which the temporal variation of concentration and temperature was considered without explicitly resolving spatial gradients.

First Version of the Model:

In the initial model, the degradation of Reactive Black 5 was represented using a pseudo–first-order kinetic expression with respect to dye concentration. This assumption is commonly used in electrooxidation studies under conditions where the concentration of oxidizing species remains relatively stable^{(2), (5), (11)}.

The rate of degradation is expressed as:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = -kC$$

where C is the dye concentration and k is the apparent rate constant.

The species balance for the system is given by:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = r$$

where r represents the reaction rate.

The thermal behaviour of the system was initially presumed as a simple energy balance equation, assuming uniform temperature within the reactor:

$$\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = Q$$

where ρ is density, C_p is specific heat capacity, and Q represents heat generation associated with the reaction.

Heat generation was assumed to be proportional to the reaction rate:

$$Q = -\Delta H \cdot r$$

Second Version of the Model:

In the second version, the model was modified to include the temperature rise observed during electrooxidation. The reaction kinetics were coupled with thermal behaviour to better reflect the experimental conditions.

This system was represented using a lumped energy balance:

$$P = C \frac{dT}{dt}$$

where P is the net thermal power and C is the thermal capacitance of the system.

The thermal capacitance is defined as:

$$C = V\rho C_p$$

where V is the reactor volume.

In this formulation, the rate constant is treated as an effective parameter influenced by temperature, allowing improved agreement with experimental observations^{(5), (12), (14)}.

2.3.4. Boundary Conditions and Initial values

A time-dependent, non-spatial model was used to simulate the direct electrooxidation of Reactive Black 5 (RB5) in a well-mixed batch system. The process was characterized by direct anodic oxidation, where hydroxyl radicals (\bullet OH) generated at the anode act as the primary oxidants. Complete mineralization of RB5 was assumed. The following overall reaction was incorporated in its final balanced form:

Within the model, the electrochemical behaviour was represented using pseudo first order kinetic expressions derived from experimental data rather than openly including the applied potential. As performed in similar studies, initial conditions like RB5 concentration, electrolyte composition, and pH, were defined based on experimental values to ensure consistency and stable simulation of time-dependent degradation behaviour^{(7), (8), (13), (20)}.

3 Results and Discussion

Model Validation and Calibration

Model validation was carried out. Predictions from the model were compared with experimental COD reduction data obtained under similar operating conditions to assess their compliance.

3.1 Comparison with Experimental work

3.1.1. Comparison of results of first version

- The first model was developed to capture intrinsic COD reduction kinetics, with simulated and experimental trends across 400–800 ppm compared in Figure 2 (a).
- At lower concentrations (400 ppm), the model shows reasonable agreement with experimental data, particularly during early and mid-time intervals (Figure 2(a)).
- With increasing concentration (500–800 ppm), the model progressively diverges, consistently overpredicting COD removal. The deviation is most evident at 800 ppm, where 85–90% removal is predicted as compared to experimental values of obtained which is in the range of 45–50% (Figure 2(a)).
- This mismatch is because of a decrease in the effective rate constant at higher pollutant loads. It may probably be influenced by limited oxidant availability and electrode surface effects not captured in the initial model.

- A significant temperature rise ($\approx 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 90°C) was observed experimentally, but is not accounted for in the isothermal model, contributing to the observed discrepancies.
- These limitations indicate the need to incorporate thermal effects, which was addressed in the refined model.

3.1.2. Comparison of results of second version

- The revised model shows lesser difference with experimental COD reduction results across the concentration range under study, as illustrated in Figure 2(b).
- At 400 ppm, simulated and experimental curves nearly overlap. For 500–600 ppm, the model accurately captures both the progression and final COD reduction, while at 700 ppm, earlier overprediction is significantly reduced and the plateau behaviour is better represented (Figure 2(b)).
- Use of an adaptive rate constant that includes temperature-driven variations during the reaction has brought significant improvements. Unlike the earlier static approach, the kinetic parameters were adjusted to reflect real-time thermal conditions.
- Incorporating temperature effects allows the model to respond more realistically to the observed temperature rise, thereby resulting in better predictions and improved representation of both concentration dependent kinetics and its thermal nature.
- The enhanced agreement between simulation and experimental data highlights the effectiveness of the updated modelling framework. A statistical evaluation using RMSE and nRMSE is presented in the following section.

Fig 2. (a) % COD reduction vs Time comparison plot for concentrations ranging from 400 ppm to 800 ppm for first version of model. (b) % COD reduction vs Time comparison plot for concentrations ranging from 400 ppm to 800 ppm for second version of model

3.2 Statistical methods for establishing results of comparison

The deviation between simulated and experimental results was quantified using RMSE and normalized RMSE (nRMSE). By calculating RMSE and nRMSE, it becomes possible to numerically quantify these deviations and evaluate how effectively the refined model captures the experimental behaviour. Such statistical assessment is a crucial step in validating the calibration process and improving the reliability of the model predictions^{(24), (25)}. The same has been shown here for the two versions of models and their results in the following sub sections.

3.2.1. First Version

- In the initial model, thermal effects and exothermicity were not considered. RMSE and nRMSE values were evaluated across concentrations ranging from 400 to 800 mg/L, as shown in Figure 3.
- RMSE values showed a gradual increase with concentration (Figure 3). That was indicative of growing deviation between simulated and experimental results. This trend is expected, as the absence of thermal effects limits the model's ability to capture changes in reaction behaviour at higher concentrations.
- The nRMSE values show a non-linear pattern (Figure 3). A noticeable surge at around 600 mg/L, followed by a slight decrease and then another increase at 800 mg/L was seen. Such fluctuations suggest inconsistency in model accuracy across the concentration range.
- This behaviour may probably be due to limitations in the kinetic representation and the absence of thermodynamic feedback in the model, particularly under conditions where temperature effects become more evident.
- Thus, the need to incorporate temperature-dependent kinetics in the modelling framework becomes essential. For exothermic systems such as Reactive Black 5 electrooxidation, inclusion of thermal effects is important to improve predictions and overall model reliability.

Fig 3. RMSE vs Concentration and nRMSE vs Concentration plot for concentrations ranging from 400 ppm to 800 ppm for first version of model

3.2.2. Second Version

- Better predictions are obtained owing to the inclusion of temperature rise and exothermicity of the reaction in the modified model. A clear improvement in predictive accuracy across the studied concentration range is seen. This improvement is seen from the comparison of RMSE and nRMSE values presented in Figure 4.

- RMSE values show a decrement with increasing concentration. The values reduce from approximately 0.21 at 400 mg/L to around 0.1 at 800 mg/L. This is in complete contrast to the initial model. There RMSE values increased with concentration. The observed reduction suggests that the thermally coupled model considers the actual experiment behaviour more effectively as thermal effects become more significant.
- The nRMSE trends further support this improvement. In the earlier model, nRMSE showed irregular variation with noticeable spikes at intermediate concentrations (e.g., around 600 mg/L). In the revised model, this variation becomes steadier. The values remain within a narrower range of approximately 12% to 20%, compared to earlier values reaching 50–55% (Figure 4).
- These observations highlight the importance of incorporating thermodynamic effects into the model. The exothermic nature of Reactive Black 5 electrooxidation influences reaction kinetics. Consideration of temperature-dependent rate constants allows the model to better represent actual system behaviour, particularly at higher concentrations.
- The more stable nRMSE behaviour also shows reduced relative error and enhanced consistency across concentrations. This strengthens confidence in the model for predictive simulations and supports its use in similar optimization studies in future.

Fig 4. RMSE vs Concentration and nRMSE vs Concentration plot for concentrations ranging from 400 ppm to 800 ppm for second version of model

3.3 Kinetic Behaviour and Mineralization

It has been seen that electrooxidation of Reactive Black 5 follows a pseudo first order kinetics. This is supported by the linear nature of $\ln(\text{COD}_0/\text{COD}_t)$ versus time plot ($R^2 \approx 0.9957$) in Figure 5. The dye molecules gradually break down into smaller and stable compounds like carbon dioxide, water, and inorganic ions like sulphates and nitrates. This is reflected in the steady reduction in COD values during the experiments. The mechanism is primarily driven by hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) generated at the MMO anode surface. These radicals attack azo bonds and aromatic structures, leading to progressive oxidation and mineralization of the dye molecules⁽⁴⁾. Thus, COD reduction provides a more reliable indication of treatment than colour removal alone.

3.4 Model Performance and Key Observations

Experimental and simulation COD removal study results show how the reduction takes place at different initial concentrations. The system shows effective results at lower concentrations around 400 ppm with rapid degradation. The efficiency of COD

Fig 5. $\ln(\text{COD}_o/\text{COD}_t)$ vs T plot for establishing first order of reaction

removal reduces with increase in concentration levels. COD reduction limits itself at higher levels. This behaviour has been widely reported in electrooxidation systems, where higher pollutant loads lead to reduced availability of reactive oxidizing species and increased process limitations^{(4), (5)}. A simultaneous rise in temperature was also observed during the experiments. This speeds up the reaction initially but does not fully remove the limitations observed at higher concentrations. The first version of the model captures the general trend reasonably well, especially at lower concentrations. However, overpredicted COD removal when the system moves away from ideal conditions is a major issue. The second version, which incorporates thermal effects lesser discrepancy with experimental data across all concentration ranges. Thus, it can be concluded that temperature plays a more important role than initial assumption.

3.5 Comparative Analysis of Model Predictions

The isothermal model is a simplified model. It works in limited concentration ranges only. It does not fully account for the changes that occur as the system depicts exothermicity during operation. Whereas the temperature integrated model responds more accurately to variations in operating conditions. It captures both the faster degradation at lower concentrations and the slower degradation at higher concentrations. This improvement is mainly due to the inclusion of temperature effects, which are known to influence electrochemical reaction kinetics significantly^{(15), (16)}.

3.6 Statistical Evaluation

To understand the difference between the model predictions and experimental data, RMSE and nRMSE were used. These metrics are commonly applied in model validation studies to assess prediction accuracy and consistency^{(24), (25)}. The first model shows increasing RMSE values with concentration and noticeable variations in nRMSE. It indicates inconsistent performance. In contrast, the second model shows a more stable nature with nRMSE values remaining within approximately 12–20%. For systems involving coupled electrochemical and thermal effects, this level of deviation is generally considered acceptable. Experimental studies have been validated with similar metrics, and the extent of deviation has been found to be similar^{(20), (23)}.

3.7 Overall Interpretation

The progression from the first to the second model highlights the importance of incorporating thermal effects in electrooxidation studies. By including temperature dependent effects, the second model offers a more realistic representation of the system. This not only improves predictions but also enhances its applicability for process optimization and scale-up.

Similar observations regarding the importance of integrated modelling approaches have been reported in recent electrochemical wastewater treatment studies⁽⁷⁾ and the use of multiphysics platforms such as COMSOL Multiphysics® further supports the reliability of such simulation models⁽¹⁴⁾.

4 Conclusion

- Incorporating thermal effects significantly improved the model's predictions for Reactive Black 5 degradation. While the isothermal model captured general trends, it showed increasing deviation at higher concentrations thereby overpredicting COD removal up to 85–90% at 800 ppm. In contrast, the thermally coupled model aligned more closely with experimental results, where COD removal ranged from 70–75% at 400 ppm to 45–50% at 800 ppm, with RMSE reducing from 0.21 to 0.1 and nRMSE stabilizing within 12–20%.
- The observed temperature rise (30°C to 90°C) played a quantifiable role in influencing reaction kinetics, particularly at higher pollutant concentrations. Accounting for this variation enabled the model to better represent system behaviour under realistic operating conditions.
- The study demonstrates that integrating experimental observations with a thermally coupled model provides a more reliable basis for predicting electrooxidation performance across varying concentrations. This therefore reduces dependence on extensive experimentation while improving the results of model-based analysis.
- For future work, extending the model to include spatial variations through transport and fluid flow coupling may be carried out to understand reactor behaviour more accurately. In addition, validation using real wastewater systems and integration with process optimization strategies could support scale-up and practical implementation of electrooxidation systems.

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6 Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interests.

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